

6. SaxFDM-Tagung

20-21 November 2025
Dresden, Germany

Scavenger Hunt Instructions:

The first letter in each of the 11 answers can be combined to a solution phrase. Hand in your solution at the registration desk to participate in a little tombola!

Hint: Save the resource links in a designated folder in your browser. They are carefully selected to help you in your work!

1

What term refers to the practice of providing unrestricted access to and reuse of peer-reviewed academic research?

#01

Source:

<https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/open-science/open-access/>

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2

What is commonly used to uniquely and sustainably identify datasets, publications and other resources, actors and outputs of the scientific research process - making them easier to find and cite?

Source:

<https://www.pid-network.de/en/>

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3

What is the digital version of a paper-format used for documenting the conceptualization, execution and evaluation of scientific experiments, observations, tests and the research data generated in this context?

Source:

<https://zenodo.org/records/13927614>

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4

What is the acronym for the German initiative aimed at creating a national infrastructure to manage, preserve, and make research data accessible across scientific disciplines?

#04

Bonus Question: Which consortium is most relevant for you?

Source:

<https://www.nfdi.de/>; <https://www.nfdi.de/konsortien/>

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5

Which living document contains general and technical information about tools & applications developed in a research project, information on quality assurance, release and public availability as well as legal and ethical aspects that affect them?

Source:

<https://datascience.codata.org/articles/10.5334/dsj-2024-043>

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-research-software-fair4rs-wg/outputs/>

#05

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6

Which principles supplement FAIR and are intended to sensitize researchers to respect the rights and interests of indigenous peoples.

#06

Source:

<https://forschungsdaten.info/praxis-kompakt/english-pages/glossary/#c403985>
<https://ask.orgk.org/de>

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7

Which term describes the ability of different systems, devices, or applications to access, exchange, and use data in a coordinated and seamless manner?

#07

Source:

<https://book.the-turing-way.org/reproducible-research/rdm/rdm-fair.html>;

<https://forschungsdaten-thueringen.de/veranstaltung/coffee-lecture-biodivportal.html>

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8

Which guideline is formulating guiding principles for research that avoid harm to individuals and society?

#08

Source:

[https://www.konsortswd.de/en/topics/best-practices-research-ethics/;](https://www.konsortswd.de/en/topics/best-practices-research-ethics/)
<http://research-ethics.org/>

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9

What is the term for a standardized system of labeling files and data-sets to ensure consistency, clarity, and easy retrieval in research data management?

Source:

https://datadryad.org/stash/best_practices

<https://book.the-turing-way.org/project-design/filenaming.html>

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10

What type of licenses allow creators to share their work with others while retaining certain rights, thereby promoting open access and collaboration?

#10

Source:

<https://creativecommons.org/>

<https://forschungsdaten.info/themen/rechte-und-pflichten/forschungsdaten-veroeffentlichen/creative-commons-lizenzen/>

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11

What is the acronym for an initiative launched by the European Commission to provide a virtual environment for storing, sharing, and re-using scientific data and results?

Source:

<https://eosc.eu/>

<https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/>

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